

Environmental Effects of AI: Challenges, Opportunities, and Sustainable Solutions

Ritvik Uprety

February 24, 2025

Copyright © 2025 Ritvik Uprety

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16003594>

With the release of ChatGPT by OpenAI, there began a greater use of artificial intelligence globally. Along with the release of ChatGPT, many other AI models were released and had different functions and benefits. Beyond the extreme amounts of code that go into giving AI the ability to respond to prompts, AI also relies heavily on hardware aspects that consumers don't see. Often, powerful GPUs are used to handle the extreme bandwidth and computational demands to run AI models such as ChatGPT. As ongoing maintenance is required to support the hardware side, it has often been shown to have negative effects on the environment. How exactly does this happen?

AI models like ChatGPT require data centers –warehouses where the servers are kept– that consume an extreme amount of energy to allow the continuous use of AI. Due to the heavy amounts of energy data centers consume, a large carbon footprint is left behind. With researchers estimating that it releases “8.4 tons of Carbon Dioxide per year.”¹ Carbon Dioxide is a greenhouse gas, which means that it is a gas that absorbs and redistributes heat. Although this may seem purely harmful, without the presence of any Carbon Dioxide Earth would struggle to keep its temperature above freezing.² The issue with the release of excess Carbon Dioxide is that it is enhancing the natural greenhouse effect of the Earth. The enhancement of the natural greenhouse effect is what leads to global warming, which hurts the environment in many ways: it

¹ Sophie Mclean, The Environmental Impact of ChatGPT: A Call for Sustainable Practices In AI Development

² Rebecca Lindsey, Climate change: atmospheric carbon dioxide

impacts biodiversity on land and in water, increases the number of droughts and heat waves, and makes forests more susceptible to wildfires.

This graph shows the increase in both atmospheric carbon dioxide and carbon dioxide emissions

Not only do the data centers release carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, but they also heavily rely on water to keep their systems cool. Due to the extreme demands of their systems, the energy they use is converted to heat, and water is used to control temperatures. Freshwater was often used in the training stages for the AI models ChatGPT-3 and 4. Freshwater is continuously used to control temperature, where it is estimated that anywhere between 20 and 50 prompts could lead to the use of 500ml of water to keep the systems running.⁴ Not only does OpenAI's ChatGPT release massive amounts of carbon dioxide, but it also uses freshwater to keep everything running smoothly.

Yes, artificial intelligence does hurt the environment by releasing carbon emissions, using excess amounts of freshwater, and using large amounts of raw materials, but there are still ways

³ Ibid.

⁴ Ibid.

to optimize the processes to decrease the damage. This has been done by enacting regulations to reduce the environmental impact.⁵ Countries in the European Union and the United States have both taken action through legislation, but it might not have as much of an impact as hoped. AI companies can decrease the environmental impact their models have by creating more efficient algorithms. Nonetheless, creating more efficient algorithms is not as easy as it sounds and would require time to change the basic mechanics. Besides changing the algorithms, companies can also reuse and recycle the freshwater they use for cooling systems, along with reusing components to prevent an excessive amount of use of raw materials.

Green computing research led to the development of new strategies that have been found to reduce energy usage when training or using AI. These strategies involve reducing the amount of power that GPUs (hardware components that use large amounts of energy in data centers) can access, but at the same time, this reduction will increase the amount of time it will take to complete a certain task.⁶ Not only does capping the GPU's power lead to less energy usage, but it also requires less use of freshwater to cool the systems. This is because when the power is capped, the system's temperature doesn't peak as high, reducing the amount of freshwater being used as a coolant. With the addition of power capping with reusing and recycling water, companies can significantly reduce negative environmental impact. Unfortunately, when companies see the efficiency of their AI model decreasing, many tend to stay away from energy efficient strategies despite the environmental advantages.

⁵ UN Environmental Program, AI has an environmental problem. Here's what the world can do about that

⁶ Kylie Foy, New tools are available to help reduce the energy that AI models devour

Yes, to allow for a reliable and strong AI model to run properly, it will deplete resources and even contribute to further release of emissions, but artificial intelligence can also benefit the environment in various ways. There have been cases where artificial intelligence has been used to reduce energy usage in the chemical industry and has assisted with environmental monitoring and management.⁷ Artificial intelligence can be used as a tool to assist with protecting the environment, but it still harms it in ways, and whether the positives outweigh the negatives is up to interpretation.

Artificial intelligence has now blended its way into society and is being used daily by companies and people in general. With all of its benefits, it also has a lot of negative effects by placing a strain on the environment through carbon emissions and resource consumption. However, ongoing research and innovation in green computing are beginning to offer hope that things can get better. By continuing to implement new strategies, AI can continue to advance while also reducing its environmental impact.

⁷ Yuan Yao, Can We Mitigate AI's Environmental Impacts

Bibliography

“AI Has an Environmental Problem. Here’s What the World Can Do about That.” UNEP.

Accessed June 29, 2025.

<http://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/ai-has-environmental-problem-heres-what-world-can-do-about>.

Foy, Kylie. “New Tools Are Available to Help Reduce the Energy That AI Models

Devour.” MIT News | Massachusetts Institute of Technology, October 5, 2023.

<https://news.mit.edu/2023/new-tools-available-reduce-energy-that-ai-models-devour-1005>.

Lindsey, Rebecca. “Climate Change: Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide.” NOAA Climate.gov,

May 21, 2025.

<http://www.climate.gov/news-features/understanding-climate/climate-change-atmospheric-carbon-dioxide>.

McLean, Sophie. “The Environmental Impact of CHATGPT.” Earth.Org, May 31, 2024.

<https://earth.org/environmental-impact-chatgpt/>.

Yao, Yuan. “Can We Mitigate AI’s Environmental Impacts?” Yale School of the

Environment, October 10, 2024.

<https://environment.yale.edu/news/article/can-we-mitigate-ais-environmental-impacts>.